

RESULTS ACHIEVED IN THE FIELD OF SPORTS IN JIZZAKH REGION

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Currently, there are 19 children's sports schools, 4 specialized children's sports schools, 1 college of Olympic and Paralympic reserves, and 1 football skill school under the jurisdiction of the General Directorate of Sports Development in Jizzakh region.

The number of sports facilities in our region is 2952, including: 19 stadiums, 493 sports halls, 12 swimming pools (5 indoor, 7 outdoor), 1 sports arena, 393 basketball, 536 volleyball, 265 handball, 226 workout fields, 8 tennis courts, 396 football fields, 1562 mini-soccer artificial turf football fields. 731 (42 percent of them have higher education) trainers in sports schools. 142 of them are female trainers. In sports schools, 21,627 people (7,031 girls) participated in 38 types of youth sports in 1,354 groups, and 104,266 (43,774 girls) participated in 27 sports clubs in secondary schools. As a result of the support of the regional governor and sponsoring organizations, 1.6 billion soums were allocated to sports federations by sponsors. Over the past period, regional athletes have collected 44 gold, 50 silver, 55 bronze medals at international competitions, 384 gold, 482 silver, 574 bronze medals, a total of 1,589 medals at national championships and cups. 266 of them fulfilled the requirement of 1st degree, 62 candidates for master of sports, 4 master of sports. In particular, they won 2 gold, 1 silver and 1 bronze medals at the prestigious international competition "Children of Asia" held in Russia. A total of 1,410,608 people live in Jizzakh region, and currently, 425,996 people are engaged in mass sports, making up 30.2 percent of the population. 205,600 people in educational institutions, 21,627 people in the field of physical education and sports, 4,521 people in higher education institutions, 2,389 people in professional educational institutions, 8,020 people in private sports facilities, 46,783 people engaged in public sports in enterprises and organizations, 161,424 regularly participating in the competitions. population is involved in mass sports.

During the past period of this year, 6964 sports events were held in the region, and 358 thousand 721 residents (113 thousand 112 of them women, 34.0%) participated in the events. To date, there are 226 workout areas in the region (13 in Arnasai, 32 in Bakhmal, 12 in Zarbdar, 27 in Zafarabad, 5 in Zafarabad, 13 in Dostlik District, 12 in Mirzachol, 11 in Pakhtakor, 16 in Forish District, 9 in

Yangiabad, 13 workout areas in Sharof Rashidov district, 29 in Jizzakh city in Gallaorol district) were built and put into operation.

Public events held in the region

According to the minutes of the meeting No. 112 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 26, 2022, the Fund for the Development of Culture and Art under the Cabinet of Ministers, the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage, the Ministry of Sports Development, and the Jizzakh Regional Government together with the "Zomin National Nature Park" on May 28-29 of this year "Zaamin ultra" festival of culture, art and sport ultramarathon (running) was organized. In order to organize the marathon at a high level, the action plan of the regional administration was developed and directed to execution.

On May 28, the participants of the marathon were placed in tents near the "Sufa Plateau" in the "Zomin National Nature Park". The main part of the marathon started on May 29 at 07:00 in the morning. 60 foreign marathoners from 18 countries, including: France, Italy, England, Israel, Ukraine, South Korea, Japan, Russia, India, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Canada, New Zealand, Georgia and other countries, took part in the marathon, while 1140 people from different regions of our Republic participated in the marathon. visited.

In order to support the participants of the marathon during the competition, 600 family members and relatives, as well as 285 local residents and young people of Zomin district supported the participants of the marathon.

The marathon was held at distances of 2, 10, 21, and 50 km. 40 employees from the regional internal affairs department and 20 employees from the national guard department were involved in the marathon to ensure public order and traffic safety. On June 3 of this year, the regional open tournament for the prize of the district prosecutor in wrestling will be held in Bakhmal district. Wrestlers will compete in 60, 66, 73, 81, 90, 100 and absolute weights in the competition organized by the initiative of the Jizzakh Regional Government and the Regional Prosecutor's Office under the slogan "A country with many wrestlers will be powerful." Wrestlers from all regions of our republic, including the neighboring Republic of Tajikistan, participated in the competition. On May 13-14 of this year, a traditional international wrestling and belt wrestling tournament between youth and adults was held in Zarbdar district of Jizzakh region. More than 500 wrestlers from all regions of our country and neighboring Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan and Tajikistan competed for the title in this tournament held under the motto "A country with many wrestlers will be powerful."

The opening ceremony of the tournament was attended by the mayor of Jizzakh region Ergash Saliev, the prosecutor of Jizzakh region, the chairman of the regional wrestling federation Islamjon Ergashkhodjaev, the chairman of the Asian wrestling confederation Momin Muratov, the chairman of the Uzbekistan wrestling federation Ravshan Dastirov, the general secretary of the wrestling federation of Uzbekistan Alisher Eshankulov and others. Songs performed by well-known artists added grace to the event

According to the minutes of the meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 17 of June 7, 2022 on the organization and high level of the "New Breath" running competition dedicated to "Youth Day", the minutes of the meeting No. 01-1098 of June 10, 2022 and 01- Action plan No. 1099 has been developed. On June 26 of this year, a running marathon was held in our region in cooperation with the Ministry of Sports Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Youth Affairs Agency, the Athletics Federation of Uzbekistan and the regional administration.

The marathon was held at a distance of 3 km from Navoi Street in Jizzakh to Sharof Rashidov Avenue. 3250 labor veterans, disabled people, military personnel, law enforcement agencies and student youth participated in the competition. In order to ensure the safety of citizens, 121 officers of the National Guard, the Department of Internal Affairs, and the Department of Road Traffic Safety were allocated, and 2 tents were set up by the Emergency Situations Department in order to create the necessary conditions for the participants of the marathon. 100 volunteers of the Athletics Federation contributed to the marathon at a high level, in addition, 2 ambulances and 6 qualified medical workers were provided by the regional health department to medically examine elderly labor veterans and disabled people before the start of the marathon.

The Regional Culture Department provided loudspeaker devices and the participation of young pop singers. The Jizzakh military garrison supported the marathon participants at the finish area. The information service of the regional administration, the regional television and radio company Jizzakh Haqiqat newspaper covered the marathon in all social networks.

The Department of Justice organized souvenirs and a festive table for 100 participants who took part in the marathon. The following participants in the marathon: 1st place among men B. Makhkamov, 2nd place J. Boltaev, 3rd place I. Abdukarimov, 1st place among women M. Pardaeva, 2nd place D. Nazarova, 3rd place I. Sangirova, Sh.Pardaboev, the youngest boy,

Z.Mamaraimova, the youngest girl, T.Saliev, the oldest male, and L.Abdusamatova, the youngest, took pride of place.

"Olympiad of Five Initiatives"

In order to ensure the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 11, 2022 "On measures to bring the involvement of young people to mass sports in the neighborhoods to a new level" No. 193-3-0Y/22 - was developed by decision no. The "Olympiad of 5 Initiatives" competition, approved by the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Youth Agency of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Sports Development, is at the 5th stage of 9 sports (athletics, mini football, soccer, workout, chess-checkers, table tennis, volleyball and streetball) , is planned to be held with the participation of boys and girls in 5 age groups, and the inter-street stages of the competition were held in our region on April 11-28 at the sports facilities of local secondary schools. In the 1st stage of the competition, a total of 32,458 young people were involved in the competition in the age group of 7-10 years, of which 16,832 were boys and 15,322 were girls. 36,663 young people were involved in street competitions held in 5 types of sports in the age group of 11-15, 22,755 of them were boys and 13,908 were girls. 26,645 young people (20% of all young people of this age) were involved in street competitions held in 6 types of sports in the age group of 16-21, of which 16,492 were teenagers and 10,153 were girls. 13,425 young people (11.2% of all young people of this age) took part in street competitions held in 6 types of sports in the age group of 22-26, of which 8,267 were teenagers and 5,158 were girls. 3455 young people (3% of all young people of this age) were involved in street competitions held in 5 types of sports in the age group of 27-30, of which 2289 were teenagers and 1166 were girls.

On May 6-14 of this year, sectoral competitions between local neighborhoods were held in sports facilities determined by the schedule approved by local sector leaders and district (city) sports development departments. A total of 18,470 young people were involved in the competitions, of which 12,513 were boys and 5,957 were girls. .

On May 17-24 of this year, district rounds were held among 9657 boys and girls from 5 age groups who won in the sector stages of the competition based on the schedule approved by the district governor.

On June 4-11 of this year, regional level competitions in 6 sports were held in Jizzakh, 1487 young people took part in the competitions, and the winners of the competition were awarded diplomas and souvenirs by the regional government.

A total of 362 young people who took 1-2-3 places in the competitions won tickets to the Republican stage of the competition.

According to the plan of measures No. 01-1071 dated June 8, 2022 and the program approved by the governor of the region, on June 18-21 of this year, the republic championship competition in checkers was held in the building of the regional "Youth Innovation Center".

On June 18, the participants from the regions were welcomed and placed in the dormitory of Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute. The main part of the competition was held on June 19, and the winners of the competition were determined on the same day. On June 20-21, within the framework of the program, events were organized for the participants to enjoy cultural entertainment. On June 21, at 20.00, an awarding ceremony was held for the winners of the competition, the awarding ceremony ended with concert programs.

The neighborhood teams that participated on behalf of our region in the Republican stages of the "Five Initiatives Olympiad" won a total of 27 prizes and took the proud 3rd place among the teams. In order to ensure the implementation of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures for the Development of Football" No. PQ-3610 of March 16, 2018

KEY WORDS:

1. In 2021, for the first time in the history of the Uzbekistan Super League, Jizzakh's "Sogdiyona" football team finished the competition in 2nd place, and this year it is also in the leading positions. Also, participating in the transition tournaments of the Asian Champions League, finishing with the 1st place in the group, on August 17, they will compete with the Tajikistan "Khojand" team in the playoffs.

2. In the Women's Football League, the women's team of Jizzakh "Sogdiyona Women" became the champion of Uzbekistan for the first time in history in 2021, and won another historic result, the Cup of Uzbekistan. In the 2022 season, he is also leading the tournament table.

3. This year, for the first time in the history of Uzbekistan's mini football (futsal) league, Jizzakh-kenteks team won 1st place and became the champion. (finished last season in 3rd place among 14 teams for the first time in history)

4. For the first time in history, the Uzbekistan mini football (futsal) national team took part in the semi-final stage of the World Futsal Championship held in

Lithuania (Baltic) in 2021. Participated in the national team of Uzbekistan 9 out of 14 futsal players (64%) are futsal players of Huaxin Jizzakh team of Jizzakh. Also, the head coach of the national team is the head coach of the "Huakhin Jizzakh" team of Jizzakh (Bahodir Akhmedov).